

Soil and crop management

Azolla in Kwangtung province, People's Republic of China

A report on conversations with members of the Kwangtung Academy of Agricultural Sciences in Kwangchow, China, on May 26, 1977. *Thomas A. Lumpkin, research scholar, International Rice Research Institute and East-West Center University of Hawaii, Honolulu, Hawaii, USA*

Azolla imbricata is grown throughout the year in Kwangtung province, People's Republic of China. In western Kwangtung, rice farmers use a domesticated variety that they call Vietnam *Azolla*.

Rice paddies are inoculated with 3.2 t/ha of nitrogen-fixing *Azolla*. In winter and spring, when temperature is mild and the fern is free of pests, *Azolla* reaches a density of 24 t/ha. Densities are also high during summer if pesticides are used and water temperature is kept below 30°C. *Azolla* begins to die when the water temperature approaches 40°C. At the optimum temperature of 28°C, the fronds are reddish in the center and green toward the periphery.

Present research in Kwangtung province focuses on the problems of growing *Azolla* in summer. Emphasis is on application instead of basic research, and selection of cultivars is the fundamental concern. Existing cultivars were selected for tolerance for high temperature, low temperature, and insects, and for high density and rapid growth. Breeding for new cultivars is not yet possible, but is being studied in Chekiang province.

The phosphorus requirement is a major problem of *Azolla*. When phosphorus is deficient, fronds turn light yellow. Potassium and boron are usually deficient in the fields, but iron is not. Deficiency symptoms are relieved by reducing the water level so that roots can reach the soil, especially in the summer.

High temperature and insect attack also cause change in color or shape.

Optimum planting date for direct-seeded rice in the Sudan Gezira

George I. Ghobrial, senior rice agronomist, Agricultural Research Corporation, Wad Medani, Sudan

To determine the optimum planting date for direct-seeded irrigated rice in the Sudan Gezira (14°N, 33°E), six varieties of rice were selected from rice observational nurseries and planted at five dates with four replications. Grain yield and yield components were determined in a randomized complete block experiment. Cultivars planted on 1 June produced the highest grain yield (see table). Plants sown early - 15 May suffered yellowing and burning of leaf tips during the early growth stages because of high temperature and low humidity. On the other hand, cultivars sown later than 1 June were damaged by heavy rains in July and August, which caused some yield loss and nonuniform stand. In addition, low temperatures (less than 20°C) before and during panicle formation checked the growth of late-sown plants.

Effects of planting dates on grain yield (t/ha) of six rice cultivars grown at Wad Medani, Sudan, 1976.

Variety or line	Yield (t/ha) at various planting dates				
	May 15	June 1	June 15	July 1	July 15
IR298-12-1-1-1	3.1	4.8	3.1	2.2	1.8
IR1712-238-3	2.9	4.3	3.0	2.5	2.2
IR1514A-E597-2	3.0	4.2	3.0	3.0	2.6
IR2153-43-2-5-3	3.4	5.2	3.8	2.7	1.8
IR2153-26-3-5-2	4.0	4.5	3.7	2.3	2.7
Kuang Chu 15	2.6	4.6	3.6	2.3	2.9

Insects that attack *Azolla* are larvae of *Micropsectra polypedium*, *Nymphula tarvata*, and *Pyralis* sp. The red or white larvae of *M. polypedium* are the most destructive. Aquatic weeds found in association with *Azolla* are *Nymphaea* sp., *Pistia straticetes*, and *Eichhornia crassipes*.

Azolla is used as pig and fish feed but

Temperature and rainfall distribution (av. of 30 years) at A.R.C., Wad Medani, Sudan.

The climatic conditions for rice seeded around 1 June are suitable during the entire growing season. The temperatures range from 21 to 32°C. Most of the rain falls between the maximum-tillering and panicle-formation stages; rains cease by the time plants reach maturity (see figure). ❧

not for human consumption. To pigs, *Azolla* is fed fresh or in a silage mixed with corn husk and bran.

At least one national conference relating to *Azolla* is held annually and other conferences are conducted at the provincial and district levels. Peasants are invited to all conferences to report on their experiences with *Azolla*. ❧